

HIGH TEMPERATURE COMPRESSIVE DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR OF SiC_w/6061Al COMPOSITE AT LIQUID-SOLID DUAL PHASE ZONE

L. Geng, J. Q. Hu and B. Liu

*P.O. Box 433, Department of Materials Science, Harbin Institute of Technology,
Harbin 150001, P.R. China.*

SUMMARY: The SiC_w/6061Al composite was fabricated by squeeze casting technique, and the compressive plastic deformation behavior of the composites was investigated at the liquid-solid dual phase temperature zone (560°C ~ 640°C). There are three stages in the true stress-strain curves of the composites. The first stage is a elastic stage; the second stage is a soften stage, and at lower temperature (such as 560°C) a peak appears in the stress-strain curve, which is due to the rotation and broken of the whiskers; the third stage is a strengthening stage which is coincident with the work hardening of the matrix alloy. With increasing strain rate, the second stage is enhanced, and a obvious peak is formed in the stress-strain curve when the strain rate reach 1.0s⁻¹. SEM results show that most of the SiC whiskers rotates to the direction perpendicular to the applied load direction, and some whiskers were broken during the plastic deformation.

KEYWORDS: silicon carbide, whisker, aluminum, high temperature, plastic deformation

INTRODUCTION

High temperature plastic deformation forming is one of the most important technique for the application of the SiC_w/Al composite. Recently, it was found that the SiC_w/Al composites exhibit a very high plastic deformation ability at the liquid-solid dual phase zone temperatures of the matrix aluminum alloy [1,2]. Many works have been done about the tensile deformation behavior at the dual phase temperatures of the SiC_w/Al composites [1-6]. However, in order to provide a basis for the applications of the high temperature plastic deformation forming, it seems more important to study the compressive deformation behavior at the dual phase temperatures of the SiC_w/Al composites.

Optimum superplasticity is often attained in practice at very low strain rates, of the order of 10⁻³s⁻¹. However, it was demonstrated by Nieh et al. [1] that it is possible to achieve superplastic-like flow and tensile elongation of up to 300% in a 20vol.% SiC_w/2124Al composite at a 525°C using a strain rate of 3.3×10⁻¹s⁻¹. High strain rate superplasticity provides a practical route for the plastic forming of the SiC_w/Al composite, and at the liquid-solid dual phase zone temperatures, the high strain rate superplasticity becomes easy to be realized.

So far, most of researches about high strain rate superplasticity are on the composites fabricated by powder metallurgy. Recently more and more works have been carried out on the

composites fabricated by squeeze casting route which has industrial advantages in many respects [2,3,5]. However, all the works are done using tensile tests, and there is no report using compressive tests. In fact, compressive test is more similar to the practical processes of the plastic forming of the composites. The objective of this paper is to investigate the compressive plastic deformation behavior of the squeeze casting SiCw/6061Al composites at the liquid-solid dual phase zone temperatures ($560^{\circ}\text{C} \sim 640^{\circ}\text{C}$) using high strain rates ($0.12 \sim 1.00\text{s}^{-1}$).

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The SiCw/6061Al composite used here was fabricated by using β -SiC whisker (TWS-100) as the reinforcing element and the commercial 6061 alloy as the base metal. Squeeze casting technique was used for fabricating the composite. Mold and whisker preform temperature, pouring temperature and applied pressure were 450°C , 750°C and 60MPa , respectively. The whisker volume fraction (V_f) is 20%.

The solidus temperature of the matrix alloy in the composite, around which the test temperatures were chosen, was measured to be 580°C by DSC technique. The compressive deformation tests were conducted in air over the temperature range of 560 to 640°C with 20°C interval using the strain rate of 0.12s^{-1} . More high strain rates, such as 0.37 , 0.56 and 1.00s^{-1} , were also adopted with a fixed deformation temperature to study the effect of strain rate on the compressive deformation behavior of the SiCw/Al composites. The microstructure of the deformed composites was observed by SEM.

Fig.1: True stress-strain curves of the SiCw/6061Al composites and 6061Al with a strain rate of 0.12s^{-1} at different temperatures, (a) 540°C , (b) 560°C , (c) 580°C , (d) 600°C , (e) 620°C , (f) 640°C .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The true stress-strain curves of the SiCw/6061Al composite and 6061Al obtained in the compressive condition at different temperatures with a strain rate of 0.12s^{-1} are shown in Fig.1. It can be seen that there are three stages in the curves. The first stage is elastic stage, in which the stress increases linearly with increasing strain. It can also be seen that the maximum stress in the first stage decreases with increasing temperature, and when the temperature is higher than 600°C , the first stage becomes not clear.

Fig.1 also shows that there is not distinguish three stages in the true stress-stain curves of the 6061Al, and in the low strain stage, the 6061Al has a lower resistance to the compressive deformation. This indicates that the high deformation resistance of the SiCw/Al composite in the first stage comes mainly from the SiC whiskers. Interface plays a very important role to ensure an effective function of the SiC whiskers. The load transfer ability of the SiC-Al interface decreases with increasing temperature because of the soften of the matrix. When the temperature is higher than 600°C , more and more liquid phase appears in the matrix, and the liquid phase prefer appears near the SiC-Al interfaces. With increasing temperature, more and more whiskers are surrounded by liquid phase, resulting in the losing of the load bearing ability of the whiskers. Therefore, the first stage gradually disappear when the temperature is higher than 600°C as shown in Fig.1.

The second stage is a soften stage, which can be seen clearly in the true stress-strain cures of the SiCw/Al composite deformed at the temperature lower than 600°C . From the true stress-strain curves of the 6061Al, it can be seen that there is also a soften stage in the same strain range, which is resulted from the dynamic recovery. Therefore, dynamic recovery of the matrix alloy is one of the reasons resulting in the soften of the SiCw/Al composite in the second stage.

Whisker rotation and broken is also one of the reasons leading to the soften of the SiCw/Al composite [7]. At lower temperature, the matrix alloy has a higher strength to limit the whisker rotation, so it needs a higher stress to made the whisker rotation. When the stress is high enough, more and more whiskers began to rotate to the direction perpendicular to the compressive load direction, resulting in a decrease of the flow stress of the composite, so a peak is formed in the true stress-strain curve in this case, as shown in Fig.1(a). With increasing temperature, the strength of the matrix alloy decreases, and more and more whiskers can rotate under a lower stress, so the peak in the stress-strain curve of the SiCw/Al composite gradually disappears.

Fig.2 is SEM photos showing the whisker distribution in the SiCw/Al composites deformed at different temperatures. All the photos were taken in the direction perpendicular to the compressive direction. It can be seen that almost all the SiC whiskers rotate to the direction perpendicular to the compressive direction. Some broken SiC whisker can also be found, especially in the composite deformed at lower temperature. The whisker broken can also leads to the soften of the composite and therefore contributes to the peak in the stress-strain curves.

The third stage is a strengthening stage. In this stage the matrix alloy is strengthened by work hardening, which leading to the increase of the flow stress of all the SiCw/Al composite in the third stage.

Fig.2: SEM photos showing the whisker distribution in the SiCw/Al composites deformed at different temperatures, (a) 540°C, (b)580°C, (c)620°C

The effect of deformation temperature on the flow stress at the strain of 0.35 is shown in Fig.3. It can be seen that the flow stress decreases with increasing temperature, and at 600°C there is a sharp decrease, especially for the SiCw/Al composite. Fig.3 indicates that the flow stress is much lower if the deformation is carried out at the liquid-solid dual phase temperatures.

Fig.3: Effect of deformation temperature on the flow stress of the SiCw/6061Al composite at the strain of 0.35

Fig.4: True stress-strain curves of the SiCw/6061Al composites deformed at 600°C with strain rate of 0.37(a), 0.56(b) and 1.0s⁻¹(c)

Fig.5: SEM photos showing the whisker distribution in the SiCw/Al composites deformed at 600°C with strain rate of 0.37(a), 0.56(b) and 1.0s⁻¹(c)

In order to study the effect of strain rate on the deformation behavior of the SiCw/Al composite, the compressive tests were also carried out for the composite at 600°C with strain rate of 0.37, 0.56 and 1.0s⁻¹. The true stress-strain curves of the composite in these conditions are shown in Fig.4. It can be seen that in the strain rate range of 0.12 to 0.56s⁻¹, the strain rate does not affect the deformation behavior of the composites. However, when the strain rate reaches 1.0s⁻¹, a peak appears in the true stress-strain curve. The sharp decrease of the flow stress means a high speed rotation of the whisker and a great amount of broken of whisker (as shown in Fig.5). Therefore, although the SiCw/Al composite can be plastic deformed in the liquid-solid dual phase temperatures without any cracks with a strain rate of 1.0s⁻¹, it is also not suitable to deform the composite with a strain rate higher than (or equal to) 1.0s⁻¹, because the whisker broken may lead to the decrease of the properties of the SiCw/Al composites.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The SiC/6061Al composite fabricated by squeeze casting route can be hot-compressed in the liquid-solid dual phase temperatures with a high strain rate from 0.12 to 1.00s⁻¹ without any cracks.
2. There are three stages in the true stress-strain curves of the SiCw/Al composites. The first stage is elastic stage, in which stress increases linearly with increasing strain; the second stage is a soften stage, which is resulted from the dynamic recovery of matrix alloy and whisker rotation and broken; the third stage is strengthening stage, which is because of the work hardening of the matrix alloy.
3. All the SiC whiskers rotate to the direction perpendicular to the compressive direction during the compressive deformation, and some broken whiskers are also found by SEM.
4. strain rate has no effect on the deformation behavior of the SiCw/Al composite within 0.12 to 0.56s⁻¹. When the strain rate reaches 1.0s⁻¹, a peak appears in the stress-strain curve, which means a high speed rotation and a great amount of broken of the whiskers.

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